

MALATE COMPLEX OF TRIVALENT ANTIMONY

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The evidence of the existence of a malate complex of trivalent antimony (complex III) containing one malate ligand per atom of antimony has been obtained by the solubility method. The equilibrium constant of the reaction by which the complex is formed from the antimonyl ion and malate ion has been determined. The mean value of the constant is 1.730×10^7 .

Attempts have been made (Henderson and Barr, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 1452; Brahmachari, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1923, 11, 207) to prepare antimonyl malates by refluxing antimony oxide with aqueous solutions of bimalates. Different investigators appear to have secured different products.

Citrate ligand has recently been found to occupy three co-ordinate positions in antimony citrate complex (Das and Pani, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 537).

In malic acid the asymmetric carbon atom is joined to one -COOH, one -OH, one -CH₂CO₂H and one H atom. If the hydrogen atom is replaced by another -CH₂CO₂H group, citric acid is obtained. It has been seen from the quantitative investigations carried out in this laboratory that the α -hydroxy group and the carboxyl group (to which the hydroxyl group is in α -position) are most suitable for the formation of a five-membered ring with antimony.

Since the citrate ligand occupies three co-ordinate positions, the carboxyl group to which the hydroxyl group is in α -position, the hydroxyl group and one of the remaining carboxyl groups react with the antimony atom and there are one five- and one six-membered ring. It can, however, be possible that there are two six-membered rings. To verify this, it was thought worthwhile to investigate the complex of antimony with malic acid. If two six-membered rings are favoured, malate ligand would be bidentate, and accordingly a malate complex containing two malate ligands per atom of antimony would be formed. If, however, the formation of a five- and a six-membered-ring is favoured, the malate ligand would be tridentate, and 1:1 complex would be formed, since the co-ordination number of antimony is found to be four in all complexes with hydroxyl and polybasic acids (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 588, 593; 1955, 32, 217).

EXPERIMENTAL

Approximately a 0.25M solution of malic acid was prepared and standardised against standard NaOH solution (standardised against a standard succinic acid solution). A known volume of the malic acid solution was taken and the calculated amount of NaOH was added to neutralise the acid to definite extents (1/6, 1/4, 1/3, 1/2, 3/4). The neutralised

solution was then diluted to different extents. The solubility of antimony oxide in these solutions was determined at 35° after Das and Pani (*loc. cit.*). The antimony contents of the solutions were determined by titrating a known volume of the solutions against a standard bromate solution. The p_H was measured by a Marconi p_H -meter. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Series.	[M].	[M(OH) ²⁻] × 10 ² .	[SbC].	p_H .	$K \times 10^7$.	K_b
3/4	0.1125	5.676	0.01372	4.82	2.073	2.876 × 10 ⁷
	0.1000	5.960	0.01150	5.00	2.506	5.262
	0.0875	5.072	0.00912	4.95	2.081	3.895
	0.0650	3.854	0.00686	4.78	2.208	4.428
	0.0525	3.032	0.00526	4.94	1.964	3.592
	0.0400	2.317	0.00381	4.86	1.654	2.516
1/2	0.1125	1.926	0.01809	4.14	2.121	6.146 × 10 ⁶
	0.1000	1.401	0.01506	4.04	1.531	3.525
	0.0875	1.377	0.01269	4.08	1.439	3.632
	0.0650	0.659	0.00988	3.90	1.547	2.580
	0.0525	0.693	0.00857	4.02	1.681	3.697
	0.0400	0.561	0.00601	4.04	1.527	3.515
1/3	0.1125	1.234	0.01861	3.94	1.707	3.121 × 10 ⁶
	0.1000	1.162	0.01560	3.96	1.595	3.035
	0.0875	1.038	0.01383	3.97	1.614	3.162
	0.0650	0.790	0.01025	3.98	1.609	3.227
	0.0525	0.668	0.00826	4.00	1.607	3.375
	0.0400	0.532	0.00628	4.02	1.603	3.526
1/4	0.1125	0.477	0.01954	3.58	2.024	1.617 × 10 ⁶
	0.1000	0.455	0.01840	3.61	2.137	1.828
	0.0875	0.413	0.01560	3.62	2.044	1.789
	0.0650	0.343	0.01166	3.66	2.019	1.968
	0.0525	0.307	0.01000	3.68	2.022	2.033
	0.0400	0.218	0.00699	3.67	1.946	1.912
1/6	0.1125	0.182	0.01614	3.03	1.235	2.778 × 10 ⁶
	0.1000	0.162	0.01407	3.03	1.208	2.715
	0.0875	0.124	0.01249	2.98	1.260	2.506
	0.0650	0.056	0.01000	3.00	1.351	2.837
	0.0525	0.083	0.00782	3.02	1.294	2.845
	0.0400	0.069	0.00606	3.06	1.304	3.145

There are two possibilities of the reaction, namely, the ligand may behave as bidentate like lactate, or tridentate like citrate. Besides, bimalate or the malate ions might be taking part in the reaction. It is therefore necessary to take all the possible reactions into account. The following four reactions, (a), (b), (c) and (d), are possible, assuming antimonyl ion (SbO⁺) to be reacting with n bimalate ions (HM(OH)⁻) or n malate (M(OH)²⁻) ions and the ligands are bidentate or tridentate. The equilibrium constants are given by the equations (a-1), (b-1), (c-1) and (d-1) respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{SbC}] \times [\text{H}^+]^{(n-2)}}{[\text{SbO}^+] \times [\text{HMIOH}^-]^n} = K_a \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (a-1)$$

$$\frac{[\text{SbC}] \times [\text{H}^+]^{(2n-2)}}{[\text{SbO}^+] \times [\text{HMIOH}^-]^n} = K_b \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (b-1)$$

$$\frac{[\text{SbC}] \times [\text{H}^+]^{(n-2)}}{[\text{SbO}^+] \times [\text{MIOH}^{2-}]^n} = K_c \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (c-1)$$

$$\frac{[\text{SbC}] \times [\text{H}^+]^{(n-2)}}{[\text{SbO}^+] \times [\text{MIOH}^{2-}]^n} = K_d \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (d-1)$$

$[\text{SbC}]$, $[\text{HMIOH}^-]$, $[\text{MIOH}^{2-}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{SbO}^+]$ represent the molar concentration of the complex, bimalate ion, malate ion, hydrogen ion and antimonyl ion respectively. It is assumed that only one of the above reactions takes place and the complex (SbC) is formed. The equilibrium constants of the reactions (c) and (d) are the same; it is therefore not possible to judge from the constancy of the equilibrium constant the number of co-ordination positions occupied by the malate ligand. If the complex is 1:1, the malate

ligand most probably occupies more than two, *i.e.* three, positions in the co-ordination sphere. If, however, the complex contains two malate ligands per atom of antimony, the malate ligand would be expected to be bidentate.

In each set of experiments the p_n is very nearly constant. Taking the p_n to be constant and substituting $[SbO^+]$ by $7.7 \times 10^{-4} \times [H^+]$ (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 2353), it can be shown that the equation (I) holds for reactions (a) and (b) for each set of experiments.

$$\frac{[SbC]}{[HMIOH^-]^n} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (I)$$

Substituting the value of SbO^+ in equation (c-1) or (d-1) and $[MIOH^{2-}]$ by $k_2 \times [HMIOH^-]/[H^+]$, where k_2 is the second dissociation constant of malic acid, it can be shown that equation (I) also holds for the reactions (c) and (d) for each set of experiments. Taking the logarithm of both sides, the equation (I) can be written as

$$\log [SbC] = \log K_1 + n \log [HMIOH^-] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (I-1)$$

If $\log [SbC]$ is plotted against $\log [HMIOH^-]$, a straight line would be obtained and the slope would give the value of n .

Since the solubility of antimony oxide in water is very small, the whole of the antimony in the solution is assumed to be present as a complex. The total malate $[M]$ in the solution is present as undissociated malic acid (H_2MIOH), bimalate ion, malate ion and the malate present in the complex. Hence,

$$[M] = [H_2MIOH] + [HMIOH^-] + [MIOH^{2-}] + n [SbC] \quad \dots \quad (I-2)$$

$$\text{or,} \quad [M] - n [SbC] = [HMIOH^-] \times \left\{ \frac{[H^+]}{k_1} + 1 + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (I-3)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the first and the second dissociation constants of malic acid. Taking k_1 and k_2 to be 5.5×10^{-4} and 2.1×10^{-5} (Cannon and Kibrick, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 814) respectively and assuming n to be equal to 1 and 2, two sets of values of $[HMIOH^-]$ are calculated. The two sets of values do not differ much since $[SbC]$ is small compared to $[M]$, and the differences in the log values are still smaller. The $\log [SbC]$ values are plotted against the corresponding $\log [HMIOH^-]$ values. Very nearly straight lines are obtained in both the cases and the slope is very nearly 1 in all the four sets of experiments. The complex therefore contains one malate ligand per atom of antimony and the ligand is most probably tridentate.

The reaction (b) or (d) might be taking place. The complex formed by the equation (b) might be complex (I) or (II), as shown below :

(Complex I)

or

(Complex II)

In either case of the formation of complex (I) or complex (II), no hydrogen ion would be liberated due to the reaction between antimonyl and bimalate ions. The value of the equilibrium constant would be the same.

The latter structure would, however, arise if the co-ordination number of antimony is four. The complex being a neutral molecule would be very little soluble. By substituting the value of n by 1, the equilibrium constant K_b is calculated. The values are fairly constant in each set of experiments (p_H is constant) but vary from one set to another set. K_b is therefore variable and the reaction (b) probably does not take place.

If the reaction (d) is considered, it becomes obvious, that a malate ligand would furnish only one hydrogen ion, and it would not be possible to remove the oxygen atom of the antimonyl ion as water molecule. Therefore, a hydroxyl group would remain attached to the antimony atom. It might also be possible that a hydroxyl group would be liberated due to the formation of the complex. The latter appears to be less probable since the solubility of antimony oxide at the beginning increases with increasing p_H . This latter complex would be the same as complex (I), supposed to be formed by the interaction of antimonyl ion with bimalate ion. It is therefore not necessary to consider this again since it can be shown that the value of the equilibrium constant would be a constant multiple of K_b . It is therefore assumed that hydroxyl group remains attached to the antimony atom. The reaction is represented by equation (II) and the equilibrium constant K by equation (II-1).

(Complex III)

$$\frac{[\text{SbC}]}{7.7 \times 10^{-4} \times [\text{H}^+] \times [\text{MIOH}^{2-}]} = K \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(II-1)}$$

The values of K are shown in Table I. It is interesting to note that the values are not only constant at a constant p_H but remain constant throughout the p_H range of investigation. The complex is therefore represented by complex (III) and the reaction, by equation (II).

The mean value of the equilibrium constant is 1.730×10^7 . The results obtained support the structure of the citrate complex proposed by Das and Pani (*loc. cit.*).